

Learning from the Early Christians to Proclaim the Christian Faith *Nishant A. Irudayadason*

Abstract

This paper explores the possibility of taking inspiration from the early Christians to live Faith in our contemporary times, which in many ways poses similar challenges to the practising Christians in different parts of the world. Some similarities are striking especially in the way Christianity has been perceived and the power of change that Christianity is able to bring about from within a society that is oppressive. History has shown that Christians thus have not lost the gospel message of being the light of the world and the salt of the Earth.

Introduction

The study of the first Christian communities can help understand the present-day reality of Christianity. What is the point of studying the first Christian communities? Is it not to show backwardness by seeking in the first communities, a kind of golden age of Christianity? Is not this idea of the Christian Golden Age the one that motivated the Reformation and still sometimes makes its impact in certain spiritually toxic neo-evangelist or neo-Gnostic circles?

In addition to the purely historical interest and spiritual richness contained in the first Christian writings, the study of the first communities shows the present state of affairs of Christianity. When we observe the difficulties faced by the first Christians, the things they opposed for which they faced persecution, and their way of witnessing the Good News in a world that was often openly hostile to them, we only remember the words of Qoheleth. What has been is what will be, and what has been done is what will be done, and there is nothing new under the sun. (Qoheleth 1:9). The study of the

beginnings of Christianity could therefore shed light on our present life as Christians.

The Power of Witness

The emergence of Christianity within the Roman Empire was fascinating. How could such a small community change the world so much in a few centuries? Especially since Christianity extends not at the point of the sword but on the contrary with the sole force of witness, despite persecution.

Pliny the Younger's letter to the Emperor shows the attitude of the authorities towards the new religion. The following passage is particularly interesting: "I asked them if they were Christians. Those who confessed it, I questioned them a second and a third time, and I threatened them with torture. When they persisted, I had them executed. For, whatever their profanity, I thought that at least their obstinacy and inflexible obstinacy should be punished."

On the one hand, we can clearly see the strength of the witness of some Christians of the time. Even under the threat of torture, they do not deny their faith one iota. This power of witness was, without doubt, one of the causes of the success of Christianity. On the other hand, we also learn that others got intimidated and denied their faith since Pliny the Younger advised the Emperor to accept the repentance of those who returned to the imperial cult. , He noted that the Roman temples that had almost been deserted were again frequented from which it was easy to judge how many people could be brought back if the door to repentance was opened.

The Roman Emperor Trajan replied to Pliny that one should not actively seek out Christians, nor accept denunciations, in short, not begin general persecutions but content oneself with punishing those who proclaimed their faith and refused to sacrifice to the gods. What the Emperor Trajan meant was that one could be a Christian as long as one was following the Christian faith discretely, without making it public and without proclaiming one's faith. All things considered, it seems to me that we can make a comparison with what we live today in our secularized society in which we can indeed be Christians but we must at all costs avoid proclaiming our faith or convictions in clear terms

While avoiding an attitude of victimization or paranoia, is it not in this perspective that we should read the political will of "neutrality" recently displayed? Is not Christianity today, as it was yesterday, in its vocation as a witness in a world that does not always accept it?

An Ancient but Ever-New Religion

In a materialistic, secularized, and disenchanting world, is not the Christian faith seen, by many, as a collection of superstitious beliefs like Nero who saw the new faith as opposing the religious characteristic of the Roman world? Though we no longer live in an Empire, the comparison with the ancient world is undoubtedly relevant. Today, perhaps more than ever, the common cult of the exaltation of selfishness, idolatry of money, and worship of reality TV is in opposition to Christian values. While ancient popular slanders often attributed to Christians the worst practices (arsonists, anthropophagi, child killers, plotters,...), it is not uncommon today for the media or “ideas that are in the air” to cast opprobrium on the Church and Christianity in general.

There is something intrinsically scandalous about Christianity, which many have expressed from the beginning but it goes far beyond the ancient socio-historical framework. In all ages, we find this type of attack against Christians in general and Catholics in particular. The genius apologist, G.K. Chesterton, describes with humour and precision the slanderous assaults on the Catholic Church by the intelligentsia of his time. Almost a hundred years apart, the contemporaneity of the description given by the English author strikes us.

If Catholicism is viewed with a bad eye, is it not primarily because the Gospel message disturbs the established order, any established order? By its radical approach, strength, fundamental freedom, and absolute generosity, the Gospel shakes up certainties and calls into question the hypocrisies and selfishness of yesterday and today. After two thousand years of existence, the Christian message does not show a wrinkle but on the contrary relevance of the most current. Chesterton says the following: “But who will explain why it is still as new to the last of the converts as it was to the first of the shepherds? It is as if a man a hundred years old entered the Olympian games among the young Greek athletes; which would surely have been the basis of a Greek legend. There is something almost as legendary about the religion that is two thousand years old now appearing as a rival of the new religions.”

Opposition to Dictatorships

If a Christian can engage fruitfully and successfully in politics, there is from the outset, in the Gospels, a clear separation between the political and the religious: “render to Caesar the things that are Caesar’s, and to God, the things that are God’s” (Mk 12:17). Even more than a separation of levels (temporal and spiritual), mistrust comes from the fact that Christians know that it is quickly

tempting to sanctify not the function but the person who occupies the function. “Do not put your faith in princes, in a son of a man powerless to save,” says the Byzantine liturgy written in a period with strong Caesaropapist tendencies. From the beginning, Christians rebelled against this practice: even more than the homage to the gods of Rome, the imperial cult appeared as a pledge of loyalty, a manifestation of unity bringing together the disparate peoples who constituted the Empire in a common tribute to the deified imperial majesty. Refusing this tribute obviously meant exposing oneself to the serious suspicion of subversive intentions.

Here again, the news is striking, the great dictatorships of the last two centuries have produced tyrants with oversized egos who, in a hysterical cult of personality, relied on technical means that a Roman Emperor would not have dared to dream of. Think of Hitler but also Stalin, Mao, or currently the Jong dynasty in North Korea. Each time, a quasi-deification of the dictator, each time, a persecution of Christians. Times change, means too, but fundamentally history, at a certain level, remains the same.

Was not Rome the first attempt at globalization, which Christianity fundamentally changed from within? In today's globalized world, in increasingly globalized governance, the role of the Christian remains the same: to refuse all idolatries and any compromise with all forms of dictatorship, however pernicious and subtle like that exercised today by the commercial world. However, Christians have always been keen to support righteous leaders and the political institution itself. As proof, the “prayer for princes and those who govern us on earth” that Clement of Rome transmitted to us. In this prayer, we can see the Christian attitude, which— despite the difficult times that the community was going through— maintained an attitude of loyalty, and optimism, hoping and praying that the imperial leaders would govern according to God's will. We can also be inspired by this strong and prayerful attitude of the early Christians.

The Epistle to Diognetus and the Urgency to Act

Two thousand years after the beginning of Christianity, the proclamation of the Good News, of love and human dignity remains the same and still shocks as much, but must be done with strength and urgency, against wind and tide if necessary. We must come out of our shells and tell others joyfully that Jesus lives and that he lives for us, even if some may perceive us as crazy people. After all, the message of the Gospel is folly, says St. Paul. But it is important

that we continue to sow hope for the millions who are in despair due to various reasons that Jesus restores life for us.

In this vein, the text of the Epistle of Mathetes to Diognetus is significant. In Chapter V, the text insists on the universality of Christians. They transcend belongings and identity claims. Christians are everywhere and live in all nations, within all cities. They have no country, no language, no custom of their own that sets them apart from the rest of the men. They inhabit the Greek cities as well as the barbarian cities according to the destiny of each. They conform to local customs for clothing, food, and the rest of existence, while manifesting the extraordinary and truly paradoxical laws of their way

In our times, during this first quarter of the twenty-first century, while provoked, Christians exhibit a strong tendency to community withdrawal and a closed sense of identity. In social media, occasionally we find Christians tend to place themselves in strong opposition to others. This extreme and closed assertion of identity loses sight of the very essence of Christianity as beautifully expressed by the Epistle to Diognetus, echoing the Gospel message to be the salt of the world. However, should not salt be mixed with food to perform its function: to give taste and flavour to life?

Many passages in the Epistle to Diognetus are thought-provoking. Another passage from this epistle speaks of Christians residing in their own homeland, but as domiciled strangers. They discharge all their duties as citizens and bear all burdens as foreigners. Every foreign land is their homeland, and every homeland is a foreign land to them. The current sad events of refugees give particular relevance to this sentence. How can we not feel fraternal compassion for the thousands of refugees thrown into exile? After all, are not we ontologically, all exiles? Are we not all in a foreign land in search of life, meaning, and love?

This epistle again refers to the family life of Christians, namely they marry like everyone else, they have children, but they do not abandon their newborns. Here again, we can only make the connection with the problems of abandonment, endemic of our time. Without judging people, as Christians, we must shed particular light on faith that cannot see life subject to utilitarian considerations. The voice of the Epistle to Diognetus shows that humanity is constantly confronted with the same trials, the same shortcomings, the same temptations and that only a different look is able to relieve the suffering that results from them.

One passage of the Epistle to Diognetus has a wonderful description of Christians: “They live in the flesh, but they are not governed by the desires of the flesh. They pass their days upon earth, but they are citizens of heaven. Obedient to the laws, they yet live on a level that transcends the law.” Here again, today as yesterday, we must show great love and patience for our societies, our fellow citizens and our brothers in humanity. Without being passive, but rooted in his faith and history, Christians must act on time. Today, as in the past, it is by striving to incarnate the values of the Gospel ourselves and to live intensely our relationship with Christ that we can be in the world as the soul is in the body.

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